

Characterization of the Interphase Width in Carbon Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Resin Composites

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SUMMARY

This study focused on the characterization of interphase region in carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites conducted by a newly developed modulus mapping test. Based on the modulus map, a non-uniform interphase region can be analyzed, as well as the local modulus gradient. Furthermore, the width of interphase can be obtained from 80nm to 270nm in different carbon fibre/epoxy systems.

Keywords: modulus mapping; interphase modulus and width; nanoindentation; nanoscratch

INTRODUCTION

Interphase is the region of significantly changed chemical composition that constitutes the bond between fibre and matrix for the transfer of loads. Within interphase region, the chemical, physical, and mechanical properties vary either continuously or in a stepwise manner between those of bulk fibre and matrix material [1]. Actually, a very detailed description of the interphase can lead to a complete understanding of the reinforcing mechanism, when combines with the corresponding adhesion analysis. Since the width and modulus of interphase greatly influenced the mechanical property as well as the durability of the whole composite [2, 3], it has been the focus of researchers for long. However, characterization of the interphase width and its modulus is fairly difficult and primarily due to the lack of appropriate techniques and the experimental difficulties required for accurate property measurements within a thickness less than 1 μm . Recently, with the development of nano-insitu technique, some methods, such as AFM, nanoindentation and nanoscratch have been introduced to achieve this goal [4-11].

There have been some literatures about the interphase width and modulus in resin matrix composites. Kim et al. characterized the interphase in glass fibre reinforced vinyl ester composites with nanoscratch and found that effective thickness of interphase varies from 0.8 μm to 1.5 μm depending on the type and concentration of silane agent [2]. Munz et al. has reported a 20-80nm width of interphase in carbon fibre/epoxy composites by measuring the stiffness using AFM force modulation mode [12]. Lee et al.

also found approximately 1 μ m wide property transition zone in cellulose fibre reinforced polypropylene composite based on nanoindentation[4]. Godara et al. identified interphase of 0.7 μ m width with modulus between fibre and matrix in carbon fibre reinforced PEEK system through nanoindentation [13]. Gao et al. detected interphase modulus in glass fibre reinforced system with atomic force microscopic phase image and nanoindentation. They found that in glass fibre/PPm composites, interphase with γ -APS/PU sizing is slightly softer than the matrix while the interphase with γ -APS/PP sizing is harder than the matrix [14]. Using the same method, Huang et al. reported that the hardness of methacryl isobutyl-POSS modified interphase is even higher than carbon fibre in CF/PAA composites [15].

Just like nanoindentation and nanoscratch, the newly developed Modulus Mapping also detects the property of material through operation of tip, which is conducted by relatively small dynamic load. Combining with the Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM), modulus mapping can provide in-situ topographic information as well as the storage and loss stiffness, storage and loss modulus, and tan delta at 256 \times 256 pixels in the image, which is equivalent to performing an indentation test at each pixel in the single image. This technique has been successfully applied in characterization of human teeth and mineral. In this study modulus mapping was first introduced in characterization of interphase of carbon fibre reinforced polymers. Based on the storage modulus gradient and its variation across the zones between carbon fibres and epoxy matrices, the width of the interphase regions were obtained in different carbon fibre/epoxy systems. In addition, the influence of fibre surface sizing agent and the full topographic character of interphase were also analyzed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Sample Preparation

The carbon fibre (CF) used in this study is T300 produced by TORAY Japan, whose tensile modulus is 230GPa with a filament diameter of 7 μ m. In order to investigate the influence of fibre surface sizing on the composite interphase, desized carbon fibres were prepared by removing sizing agent in acetone solvent. After 48 hours immersion, carbon fibres were then dried at ambient temperature and stored in dry cabinet before use.

The epoxy resin is E51 produced by Edison Corporation China. The cure agent is triethylene foramine produced by Lvbao Company, ShangHai China. In the matrix system, cure agent was mixed with the epoxy resin at weight percentage of 15%.

Composite samples consisting of unidirectional carbon fibres and epoxy resin were made by in-situ impregnation, cured at 80oC for five hours. For nanoindentation modulus mapping tests, specimens were prepared as a column with the carbon fibre yarn placed perpendicularly in the middle. The column was cut perpendicularly to the cross section into 10mm thick slice. Then the slice was polished at one side to obtain a smooth surface. To avoid erroneous results due to rough topography, the surface had to be analyzed for flatness by AFM with Ra ranging from 15nm to 20nm, which is an average

value of surface height deviation.

Modulus Mapping Test

Modulus Mapping is a newly developed instrument, which combines dynamic action with Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM) function in a nanomechanical equipment. In SPM mode, the instrument can provide in-situ images of the sample surface immediately before or after a test is performed. During the indentation test and the imaging process, the probe is oscillated sinusoidally with a given frequency and dynamic load on top of a larger quasi-static force. The resulting signal from the transducer is then analyzed to determine the displacement amplitude and phase lag of the oscillation. From this data, the stiffness can be found as a function of the position on the sample for each pixel in the image. In addition, if the geometry of the probe is known, the modulus can be calculated. In other words, modulus mapping can provide storage and loss modulus, tan delta, and storage and loss stiffness properties as a function of the position on the sample. It is equivalent to perform indentation tests at each pixel in a 256×256 image, or 65,536 tests in a single image, which is applicable in characterizing mechanical property changes within minute area around fibres.

In this study, a Hysitron nanomechanical instrument was used to conduct the modulus mapping test. Finally, a 10µm by 10µm modulus map was created of a fibre in the matrix of each measurement. The static load was 1µN with a dynamic force of 2µN oscillating at 200Hz. In comparison with the quasi-static nanoindentation, modulus mapping uses relatively small indentation force which greatly reduces the ‘fibre effect’ or ‘boundary effect’ of fibres. Therefore, it is able to precisely reflect the modulus gradients in interphase region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Modulus Mapping Characterization of Composites

During modulus mapping process, the SPM scan can form images with 256 data lines by 256 data points in each line. Figure 1 shows the height and storage modulus map of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites under dynamic nanoindentation. Figure 2 is the data of storage modulus along a horizontal line across the interphase zone in modulus map of composites. From the profile we can find that the storage modulus on the surface of cross-section carbon fibres is much higher than that of the resin matrix. Besides, the modulus value of carbon fibres scattered in a quite wide scope, while the results of bulk matrix were quite the same.

Figure 1 Typical height in-situ image (a) and the corresponding storage modulus map (b) of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resins.

Figure 2 Storage modulus data along a horizontal line in modulus map of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites.

To further analyze the properties quantitatively, the pixel amount was counted statistically for 65,536 pixels in the image. Figure 3 is a typical profile of storage modulus according to the modulus map of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites. Several observations can be made. First, two peaks of pixel counts on the left and right were attributed to the bulk of epoxy resin and the bulk of carbon fibre, respectively. Secondly, the left sharp peak demonstrated a steady storage modulus of the resin matrix. The average value is 18GPa with a 3GPa standard deviation calculated by the ‘triple

standard deviation rule'. On the contrary, the right gentle peak corresponded to the bulk of carbon fibre, which is consistent with the data in Figure 2. This wide scatter of results is probably due to the small indentation depth much shallower than the ideal conditions. The storage modulus of the equalizing value comes out to be 87GPa with the standard deviation extending to 45GPa. Thirdly, the profile in Figure 3 reveals that the storage modulus of the interphase varies between those of the epoxy matrices and the carbon fibres, from 21GPa to 42GPa, which agrees with the rule from our quasi-static nanoindentation tests and the reports of others [14].

In order to investigate the topographical character of interphase zone in composites, different colours were defined to represent gradual increased storage modulus in the modulus map. Figure 4 exhibits the full image of interphase in carbon fibre reinforced composites through modulus gradients. From the picture, we can find that regions of different materials can be clearly distinguished according to the colours of the carbon fibre, epoxy resin, and interphase, respectively. As expected, the carbon fibre was surrounded by the interphase very closely and grooves on the carbon fibre surface can even be identified. However, the image illustrates a non-uniform interphase, which might due to the fibre surface grooves and irregular distribution of sizing agent, as well as the resulting uneven distribution of curing agent.

Furthermore, areas of interphase can be achieved by counting pixels in the transition zone, besides the perimeter obtained by image processing software. Thus the average width of interphase can be calculated according to the modulus image. However, it should be pointed out that, by this method, the width of interphase could only be qualitatively analyzed because the size almost solely depends on the critical modulus value falling into the transition zone.

Figure 3 Statistic results of storage modulus of 65,536 pixels in modulus mapping of CF/epoxy composite.

Figure 4 Image of storage modulus to illustrate topographical feature of the interphase zone in CF/epoxy composite.

Width of the Interphase in Carbon Fibre Composites

To achieve a very detailed description of the interphase thickness, modulus variation across the transition region between the carbon fibre and the epoxy resin has been analyzed. Figure 5(a) shows the results. From the profile we can find that there are eight pixels located in the interphase zone, which indicate the absence of ‘fibre effect’ in modulus mapping. This might due to the relatively small indentation force in comparison with the traditional quasi-static nanoindentation. Based on the storage modulus in Figure 5(a), a 270nm wide transition zone can be calculated which represents the interphase in composites. Our nanoscratch tests indicate that the corresponding interphase comes out to be a width of 70-150nm according to the scratch depth and the friction coefficient.

In order to study the effect of fibre surface sizing agent on the interphase width, composites fabricated with desized carbon fibres were also tested by modulus mapping. The results are shown in Figure 5(b). We can find that there are no pixels falling in the transition zone in desized CF/Epoxy system, which suggested a thickness with only 80nm. In contrast with the obvious interphase region in normal composites, it could be concluded that the sizing on the surface of carbon fibre plays an important role in the formation of composite interphase with a substantial thickness. These are in accordance with Gao’s study. He has characterized the modulus profile across desized glass fibre reinforced epoxy composites by using AFM nanoindentation, but no modulus between fibres and matrix were found [14]. While in sized glass fibre/epoxy system, the modulus gradients were repeatedly observed under different indentation forces.

Figure 5 Storage modulus profiles across the interphase region between carbon fibre and epoxy resin in carbon fiber reinforced epoxy system (a), and in desized carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites (b).

CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the width of interphase region in carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin composites using Modulus Mapping combines the dynamic nanoindentation with in-situ Scanning Probe Microscopy. Modulus Mapping is the equivalent of performing an indentation test, by using relatively small indentation force at each pixel in a 256×256 image, or 65,536 tests in a single image.

The experimental results show that the nature of the composite interphase region can be obtained by modulus mapping, which is able to precisely reflect the modulus variation in interphase region without the traditional nanoindentation ‘fibre effect’. Based on the image of modulus gradient, the topographical character of interphase zone was analyzed, which illustrates a non-uniform interphase varying with the grooves on carbon fibre surface. Furthermore, the interphase in desized carbon fibre reinforced composites is much thinner than that in normal carbon fibre composites, which suggested that the formation of interphase in composites were mainly determined by the presence of sizing agent on carbon fibre surface. However, it should be pointed out that the interphase width could only be calculated roughly. In order to obtain the precise value, further study should be carried out.

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